

**THE NOTION OF “PATIENCE” AS CULTURAL AND LINGUISTIC
CROSS-BORDER PHENOMENON**

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***Abstract.** This article focuses on the definition and characteristics of the concept “patience” within the main aspects of its meaning directions, including epistemological, philosophical, linguo-cultural, cognitive and psycholinguistic ones. The attempt to combine and gather different approaches and interpretations of the concept “patience” is the main purpose of the paper. It is revealed that “patience” is one of the key concepts on which society relies, using it as a key to maintain human rights and freedoms. The genesis of “patience” in the science is related to the person’s representation of the world, the formation of abstract norms of behavior and the embodiment of this behavior in a particular life situation. In modern cognitive linguistics, studying of the concept “patience” is rather actual and controversial nowadays, as it is functionally significant for the corresponding culture. Any concept is realized in language units. We have made the semantic analysis of the word “patience” and come to the conclusion that semantic structure of it in English consists of the different meanings, forming the so-called “conceptual layer”.*

***Key words:** “patience”, aspect, concept, linguistics, culture, cognitive, linguo-cultural, conceptual layer.*

**“SABR” TUSHUNCHI MADANIY VA LINGVISTIK CHEGARAVIY
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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola "sabr" tushunchasining ta'rifi va xususiyatlari, uning ma'no yo'nalishlarining asosiy jihatlari, jumladan, gnoseologik, falsafiy, lingvo-madaniy, kognitiv va psixolingvistik yo'nalishlarga qaratilgan. "Sabr" tushunchasining turli yondashuvlari va talqinlarini birlashtirish va to'plashga urinish maqolaning asosiy maqsadidir. "Sabr" jamiyat tayanadigan asosiy tushunchalardan biri bo'lib, undan inson huquq va erkinliklarini ta'minlashda kalit sifatida foydalanishi ma'lum bo'ldi. Fanda "sabr" tushunchaning genezisi insonning dunyoni tasvirlashi, mavhum xulq-atvor normalarini shakllantirish va muayyan hayotiy vaziyatda ushbu xatti-harakatning timsoli bilan bog'liq. Zamonaviy kognitiv lingvistikada "sabr" tushunchasini o'rganish bugungi kunda juda dolzarb va munozarali, chunki u tegishli madaniy-funksional ahamiyatga ega. Har qanday tushuncha til birliklarida namoyon bo'ladi. Biz "sabr" so'zining semantik tahlilini o'tkazdik va uning ingliz tilidagi semantik tuzilishi turli ma'nolardan iborat "kontseptual qatlam"ni shakllanadi degan xulosaga keldik.

Kalit so'zlar: "sabr", jihat, tushuncha, tilshunoslik, madaniyat, kognitiv, lingvomadaniy, konseptual qatlam.

ПОНЯТИЕ «ТЕРПЕНИЕ» КАК ПОГРАНИЧНЫЙ МЕЖДУ КУЛЬТУРОЙ И ЛИНГВИСТИКОЙ ФЕНОМЕН

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Аннотация. В данной статье основное внимание уделяется определению и характеристике понятия «терпение» в рамках основных аспектов его смысловых направлений, в том числе гносеологического, философского, лингвокультурологического, когнитивного и психолингвистического. Попытка объединить и собрать различные подходы и интерпретации понятия «терпение» является основной целью статьи. Выявлено, что «терпение» является одним из ключевых понятий, на которое опирается общество, используя его как ключ к сохранению прав и свобод человека. Генезис «терпения» в науке связан с представлением человека о мире, формированием абстрактных норм поведения и воплощением этого поведения в конкретной жизненной ситуации. В современной когнитивной лингвистике изучение концепта «терпение» является весьма актуальным и противоречивым, поскольку оно функционально значимо для соответствующей культуры. Любое понятие реализуется в языковых единицах. Мы провели семантический

анализ концепта «терпение» и пришли к выводу, что его семантическая структура в английском языке состоит из различных значений, образующих так называемый «концептуальный слой».

Ключевые слова: «терпение», аспект, понятие, лингвистика, культура, когнитивный, лингвокультурный, концептуальный слой.

Introduction. The concept of “patience” has a religious philosophical meaning in almost all languages, and in turn is a lexical unit of universal nature as a national and moral-emotional concept. The linguistic study of the concept of “patience” has not yet been extensively studied in comparison with the philosophical study. Studies in different linguocultures show that the concept of “patience” represents a common concept for most peoples.

It is not a secret that worldviews are being formed on the basis of moral values, However, Islam, as one of the worldview set, encourages people to be patient and tolerant more than other sets.

Specifically, in Uzbekistan, the concept of "patience" is considered important for revealing the essence of a number of other concepts in the linguistic culture of people. The concept of "patience" reflects the worldview of that nation in different language cultures and systems of concepts. Such words act as a storehouse of *national conceptual knowledge* about the world in the form of a *national language system*. Despite the fact that these two concepts are closely related to each other, at the same time they are different, the activation of the concept of "patience" in the Uzbek language, its idiomatic meaning and aspects reflected in phraseology are highlighted.

Literature Review. Most concepts reflect the values that form of experience or truth of a certain people or nation [1]. Mainly, it means that it is based on the understanding of wisdom of the people who states that local knowledge forms of real experience as a result of integration between human, environment, and spirit [2].

In some research papers concepts form semantic centers of so-called “local wisdom” and also can be interpreted as traditional knowledge about the relationship between society and the nature, society and the science, society and the history, society and the religion, society and the world views in general [3]. All that gave birth to a value which is then internalized by the community itself.

Furthermore, some linguists define the culturally-colored concepts as knowledge and reflection of the way of life as a way or strategy in overcoming life problems that are realized by various activities carried out by local communities [4].

Some linguists and scientists believe that educating people of high moral character and integrity who adhere to universal values based on moral principles is an urgent issue of today’s science. They pay more attention to upbringing the youth via the education system and try to convey traditions. Our society is still

preserving local wisdom, such as the philosophy of "patience", "gratitude" and "sincerity". In connection with the philosophy of life that is believed by the Uzbek people, researchers are interested in critically examining the philosophy of life, one of these philosophies is directly connected to the concept of "patience" [5]. Consequently, for this group of researchers, the approach to the problem of nationally- and culturally-linked concepts is highly relevant [6].

Results and Discussion. Linguocultural modeling of concepts is one of the most actively developing areas of linguistics, at the same time, the conceptual field has not yet been a subject of special study in the science of language, the concept of "patience" and related concepts reflect important characteristics of a person's attitude to reality, however, these semantic formations are still have not been analyzed in linguistics, understanding the specifics of patience and related concepts in English and Uzbek linguocultures will allow to optimize intercultural communication.

Linguocultural concepts form conceptual fields – complex semantic formations, including several concepts, united by common features [7]. The system-forming feature of the conceptual field is a certain referential feature, which is linguistically embodied in the semantics of the word, which acts as the main name of the concept. In the conceptual field of "patience", such a sign is "reaction to unfavorable circumstances."

The conceptual field "patience" is an interconnected and interdependent unity of the notions, including "patience", "suffering", "humility", "endurance", "tolerance". The concept of "patience" acts as the semantic core of this field. The model of this field is a frame in which the signs "reaction to unfavorable circumstances", "passive emotional reaction to unfavorable circumstances", "active rational reaction to unfavorable circumstances in the form of refusal of resistance", "active volitional reaction to unfavorable circumstances in the form of readiness to overcome difficulties" an active strong-willed reaction to unpleasant circumstances in the form of agreement with other modes of thought and behavior.

"Patience" is a special Islamic quality in the world view of Uzbeks, and it has been reflected in the dictionaries of the Uzbek language for several centuries. The expansion of the conceptual components of the concept of "patience" in various ways, such as patience and endurance, shows that the concept of patience remains an integral part of the Uzbek national mentality. Analyzing the materials of various literatures and religious sites available in the modern Uzbek language, the analysis shows that today the meanings that Uzbek speakers attach to the word "patience" are wider and more colorful than before. In the minds of modern Uzbeks, being patient is also understood as the ability to move steadily and persistently towards a goal.

The most important ethno-specific conceptual differences of the concepts that form the field of "patience" are as follows:

- in the concept of "patience" the British criticize excessive patience and fatalism, the Uzbeks associate patience with courage;
- in the concept of "suffering" the British emphasize the need to endure mental and physical pain, the Uzbek describe in detail the varieties of suffering;
- in the concept of "humility", the British emphasize external calmness, and the Uzbeks – voluntary submission to fate;
- in the concept of "endurance" the British emphasize the volitional effort of a person who holds on and does not call anyone for help, the ability not to succumb to weakness;
- in the concept of "tolerance" the British emphasize the right of another person to behave in their own way, while the Uzbeks interpret this concept as an unwanted compromise.

Patience is a virtue. "A watched pot never boils". All things are difficult before they are easy. Regarding the terminological meaning of patience, the scholars have given a number of complementary definitions, and one of them is as following: "Patience is enduring emotional and mental burdens and pains."

Others interpretations are:

- "Patience is to keep the soul from sorrow and bitterness, the tongue from complaining, and the limbs from worrying".

- "Patience is one of the virtues of the soul, and it is to refrain from doing things that are good and beautiful".

- "Patience is steadfastness" in the rules of the Qur'an and Sunnah.

- "Patience is to be polite when you're in trouble".

- "Patience is the steadfastness of the heart during suffering" [8].

Such religious and philosophical definitions of the concept of "patience" are widely covered in the literature

For example, in Uzbek national proverbs, "a patient person succeeds in life", and there is a pragmatic meaning that "patience is a necessary condition for success".

Although the concept of "patience" in terms of ethno-identity has a universal nature among many peoples, in contrast to some peoples, the linguistic landscape of the world can be observed in the minds of Uzbeks. It is clear that the concept of "patience" as a core of national, social and individual consciousness is firmly rooted in the consciousness of the Uzbek language. Uzbek speakers have a broad understanding of the linguistic semantic field of the concept of "patience" and give it a unique definition. Evaluation of patience by language users is vividly reflected in the following associations: "a patient person", "a resilient person", "a person who is not in a hurry", "a heavy-handed person", "a calm person" [9].

It seems that Uzbek speakers are positive about the concept of "patience". This situation shows that "patience" is one of the most positive and national qualities of the Uzbek people.

Conclusion. To conclude, the conceptual field “patience” is a combination of several concepts that have common and distinctive semantic features, these concepts are characterized by specific conceptual, figurative and evaluative features.

References:

1. Abdullayeva M. R. Ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida semantik tarjima ma’nosini berish // Xorazm Ma’mun akademiyasi axborotnomasi. – 2022. Vol. 2. – pp. 314-316.
2. Akbarova Z. A. Concept and Linguistic Consciousness // FarSU Scientific Newsletter. – 2020. Vol. 4. – pp. 233-234.
3. Anderson J. C. The Theory of Concept. Alternative Points. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2023. – 106 p.
4. Davlatmirova M. B. Conceptual and association area of “Сабр”. Studies of tolerance among the youth of Tajikistan. – Moscow: Natural History Academy Press, 2016. – pp. 56-74.
5. Davlatmirova M. B. Patience as a major component of the Fate macroconcept in Tajik, Pamir and Arabic linguistic cultures // Science of Kazan. – 2015. Vol. 6. – pp. 121-123.
6. Dolgova I.A. Conceptual field «Patience» in English and Russian linguocuturology: PhD dissertation: 10.02.20. – Volgograd, 2006. – pp. 164.
7. Lapasov N. Sh. Comparative Analysis of Linguoculturological Features of the Concept of “Sabr” – “Patience” in Uzbek and English Languages // Analytical Journal of Education and Development. – 2021. Vol. 1(6). – pp. 321-325.
8. Sternin I. A., Rudakova A. V. Psycholinguistical meaning of word and its description. – Voronezh, 2011. – 192 p.
9. Vorkachev S. G. Methodological basis for linguistic concept studies. The aspects of metacommunicative activity: theoretical and applied linguistics // Inter-Institutional Collection of Scientific Works – 2002. Vol. 3. – pp. 79-95.
10. Whipp M. The Grace of Waiting: Learning patience and embracing its gifts. – London: Canterbury Press Norwich, 2017.